

A small step towards the epistemic decentralization of science: a dataset of journals and publications indexed in African Journals Online

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Abstract

Purpose: This paper examines African Journals Online (AJOL) as a bibliometric resource, providing a structured dataset of journal and publication metadata. In addition, it integrates AJOL data with OpenAlex to enhance metadata coverage and improve interoperability with other bibliometric sources.

Design/methodology/approach: The paper details the construction process of a database based on AJOL data, highlighting its strengths and limitations, and presents a descriptive analysis of AJOL's indexed journals and publications.

Findings: The publication analysis demonstrates a steady growth in the number of publications over time but reveals significant disparities in their distribution across African countries. The paper presents an example of the possibilities of integrating AJOL and OpenAlex, analysing the geography of authors of journals in AJOL. The analysis reveals that African journals serve as both regional and international venues.

Research limitations: While AJOL contains relevant information about African publications and journals, its metadata is limited, which also limits the kind of analysis that can be performed with the database. Also, although automatic citation procedures have been performed, the metadata has not been manually curated. Therefore, inaccuracies present in AJOL might be reproduced. The integration with OpenAlex aims to overcome some of the limitations.

Practical implications: The database contributes to the accessibility of African publications by providing structured, accessible metadata derived from AJOL. It facilitates bibliometric analyses that are more representative of African research activity and complements ongoing efforts to develop alternative data sources that better reflect the diversity of global knowledge production.

Originality/value: The paper presents a novel database for bibliometric analysis and offers a report of the retrieval and construction procedures. The inclusion of matched data with OpenAlex further enhances the database's utility. By showcasing AJOL's potential, this study contributes to the broader goal of fostering inclusivity and improving the representation of African research in bibliometric analyses.

Keywords

Decentralization of science; African journals online; African science; data paper.

1. Introduction

Although critics of hegemonic models of science are not new, the academic interest in decolonial discourses has increased in recent years. If science was once defined as an objective and universal practice, decolonial scholars have challenged this assumption, emphasizing that science, as any other human endeavor, is traversed by the cultural and sociological contexts where it is developed. Historians of science have shown that knowledge has tended to be concentrated in a few places whose theories and methods have been spread to all other countries and regions. To reverse this tendency, both the material and symbolic dimensions of the concentration processes have to be addressed. Rodríguez-Medina (2014) distinguishes decentring –which challenges the symbolic dimension of the concentration of power and resources– from decentralizing –which addresses its material dimension. He argues then that the decolonization of ideas –i.e. decentring– needs a corresponding epistemic decentralization that creates the material conditions for peripheries to challenge mainstream discourses.

Although it also has effects in other areas of the scientific knowledge production process, one of the most striking examples of the concentration of symbolic and material resources is the academic publishing system. Focusing on the material dimension, this means that most publishers, journals, and articles are concentrated in the Global North, especially in the United States and Europe –for a theoretical argumentation see Alatas (2003)–, or that English has become the lingua franca of the academic world (Lillis & Curry, 2010; Canagarajah, 1996). This concentration is also reflected in the location and the journals indexed in international journal indexing systems –namely, Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus–, which are the main sources of data for scientific evaluation, including research and funding assessments, and bibliometric analyses worldwide. However, although largely acknowledged as the only authorities in the identification of high-quality research, the status of WoS and Scopus is currently being challenged due to their various biases, including limitations in their coverage of research disciplines (Archambault et al., 2006; Larivière & Macaluso, 2011; Larivière, Haustein & Mongeon, 2015), geographical regions (Chavarro, 2018; Asubiaro, Onaolapo & Mills, 2024), and languages (van Leeuwen et al., 2001; Lillis & Curry, 2010; Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016; Vera-Baceta, Thelwall & Kousha, 2019).

The need for more inclusive and comprehensive bibliographic data sources is especially pressing in areas that have historically been marginalized in these traditional systems. Several studies have shown that Scopus and WoS fail to provide an accurate picture of global scholarly publishing (Khanna et al., 2022), with the Global South—particularly Africa—being most affected. For example, analysis of WoS data by Tijssen (2007) revealed that African authors contributed fewer than 1.5% of indexed publications between 1980 and 2004. More recent research by Asubiaro et al. (2024) found that journals from sub-Saharan Africa were the least represented in both Scopus and WoS. In an earlier study, Asubiaro & Onaolapo (2023) not only confirmed this limited representation but also emphasized the potential of alternative databases like Crossref to address these gaps. Other studies have highlighted the potential of alternative source types, such as academic networks, to study publication and collaboration patterns in sub-Saharan Africa (Harsh et al., 2021). Scholars have also highlighted the importance of

using field-specific or national citation indexes –over multidisciplinary and international databases– for certain types of analyses (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016). This recognition aligns with broader efforts reflected in the development of alternative journal indexing systems and repositories, which aim to mitigate coverage biases and promote the international recognition of regional and local research.

One of the first examples of regional journal repositories is African Journals Online (AJOL), which was launched in 1998 by the International Network for the Availability of Scientific Publications (INASP) in collaboration with the Public Knowledge Project (PKP). When it was initiated, AJOL only covered 50 African journals. In March 2024, the number of covered journals increased to 739 from 39 African countries. However, despite its extensive coverage, AJOL remains an understudied source of bibliometric data from African countries. One of the reasons for its absence from bibliometric studies is the difficulty of accessing AJOL's data. As AJOL is not a full-fledged academic database, it does not provide metadata for its articles, and it does not have an advanced search tool that allows users to build search strategies. The website is, therefore, a journal directory that allows users to browse journals' issues and volumes but prevents them from searching for specific articles or topics. In terms of bibliometric analysis, AJOL does not curate nor provide access to metadata from journals or articles. However, some metadata fields are available in AJOL's website and can be retrieved manually or using web scrapping techniques.

Recent literature has also pointed out to the potential of AJOL as a data source of bibliographic data for the African continent. Alonso-Álvarez (2024) showed that AJOL can counteract the biases in mainstream databases towards African science. However, the data source also presents its limitations, especially in terms of regions, and languages, presenting missing countries and important imbalances between countries, and mostly publications written in English. Despite these limitations, this article regards AJOL as a valuable source of information on African journals and publications and seeks to facilitate its accessibility and usability. Accordingly, the main objective of the paper is to present a publication and journal database derived from AJOL content, designed to support its use as a bibliometric data source for the study of African scholarly production. The database introduced herein provides researchers and other users with a structured, downloadable version of AJOL data that can be readily explored and analyzed. The paper also presents a comprehensive picture of AJOL data regarding journals and academic papers, and provides information about the limitations of the data. The database aims to contribute to the idea of a decentralized and federated system of sources (e.g., Babini et al., 2024). Therefore, to facilitate the interoperability of AJOL articles' data with other academic databases, the database also includes a table that matches AJOL and OpenAlex documents using the unique identifiers of each data source. The matching AJOL-OpenAlex aims to contribute towards the idea of a federation of open research information sources.

2. Data and methods

2.1 Data collection

The journal list and publications indexed in AJOL were retrieved using web scrapping techniques. The metadata of the publications was retrieved using the R package *ojsr*, which scrapes the metadata of the articles indexed in Open Journal Systems (OJS) pages from their head tag in html. For the journals' information, the data was downloaded from

various pages of the AJOL's website using *rvest* R package. Both publications' and journals' metadata were retrieved in February 2024.

2.1.1 Journal metadata

Information was retrieved from 739 journals using the *rvest* package. The metadata fields were merged together using journals titles and urls. A unique identificatory was created for each journal to join them with the publications database.

As AJOL does not provide the metadata by journal, it was retrieved from different pages within the website. This process led to some incongruencies in journals coverage. For instance, a journal might appear in the country classification but not in the research area classification. Journals that did not appear in one of the classifications were assigned NAs (Not Available information) for that field. In the case of the open access field, AJOL only reports the journals that have a Diamond access. The rest of the journals were classified as non-Diamond.

ISSNs were retrieved from each journal's AJOL site using web scraping. Eleven journals were missing both print ISSN and eISSN. Of these, three were found in the ISSN Portal, and their ISSN fields were manually added. All retrieved ISSNs were cross-checked against the ISSN Portal and were recognized by it, although some were at different stages of the validation process (e.g., awaiting validation).

As a way to increase the credibility of the journals it indexes, AJOL employs the Journal Publishing Practices and Standards (JPPS) framework, developed conjunctly by AJOL and the International Network for Advancing Science and Policy (INASP). JPPS classifies journals into six categories depending on the JPPS criteria they meet: inactive title, no stars, new title, one star, two stars, and three stars. All criteria are retrieved from JPPS website.¹ New title, one star, two stars, and three stars work hierarchically in which a higher category includes all criteria from the previous one and other additional requirements. Finally, the inactive category includes journals that are not up to date in the Journals Online System (JOL). It is worth noting that journals that do not meet JPPS criteria to belong to one of the higher levels can still appear in AJOL under the no-stars category.

Table 1 shows the number and percentage of NAs per metadata field, and the final population of journal metadata fields in the database (Final N).

Table 1. Population of journal metadata fields

Field	NAs	% NAs	Final N
Title	0	0	739
eISSN	84	11.4	655
ISSN print	334	45.2	405
country	0	0	739
JPPS status	5	0.7	734
OA	0	0	739

¹ <https://www.journalquality.info/en/>

Research area	3	0.4	736
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2.1.2 Publications metadata

In total, metadata fields from 237,263 articles were downloaded. Finally, only 223,981 articles were kept after removing publications with no metadata and duplicates. Regarding metadata, 11,767 publications had missing values (NAs) in almost every metadata field, including title, doi, and journal. In some cases, data from the 11,767 articles with missing values appears at the front end of the AJOL page. However, it has not been recorded in the html tag, therefore not being included in the database. After removing publications with no metadata, 1,515 duplicated records were found and therefore removed from the database.

The quality of the data was assessed to spot errors and clean the data. In the cases where erroneous data could be identified following an aggregate process –for instance, erroneous format (e.g., alphabetical values in pages field), non-reported missing values (e.g., instances of ‘abstract’ being the content of the field abstract, or ‘keywords’ being the content of the keywords field), etc.–, invalid data was removed. The process and all modifications are reported in the read me file of the database, along with the manual checks made in all fields.

Table 2 presents all the fields in the articles’ head tag, the missing observations for each field, and the final population (Final N column) of the fields included in the database after removing NAs, duplicates, and erroneous data as described in the paragraph above. In the case of repeated fields (ex. *DC.Identifier.DOI* and *citation_doi*), only one of them was selected as the content was identical.

Language and type were not added to the table due to the high number of errors found in the metadata.

Multiparty fields, such as keywords and authors, were split and recorded in new tables.

All source fields were removed. To link the publications table with the journal's table, and identifier was created. To link the articles’ table with the journals’ table, the common sections of the URLs of the articles and the journal pages were used. Then journal identifiers were created and added to the articles’ table.

Table 2. Population of publication metadata fields

Field	NAs	% NAs	Selected	Final N
input_url	0	0	1	223,981
DC.Creator.PersonalName	11,866	5.00	0	-
DC.Date.created	76,341	32.18	0	-
DC.Date.dateSubmitted	11,767	4.96	0	-
DC.Date.issued	11,872	5.00	1	223,876
DC.Date.modified	11,767	4.96	0	-
DC.Description	11,770	4.96	1	192,933

DC.Format	17,566	7.40	0	-
DC.Identifier	11,767	4.96	1	223,981
DC.Identifier.pageNumber	69,133	29.14	0	-
DC.Identifier.URI	11,767	4.96	0	-
DC.Language	11,767	4.96	0	-
DC.Rights	11,767	4.96	0	-
DC.Source	11,767	4.96	1	223,981
DC.Source.ISSN	13,498	5.70	0	-
DC.Source.Issue	28,964	12.21	1	206,866
DC.Source.Volume	12,298	5.18	1	223,450
DC.Source.URI	11,767	4.96	0	-
DC.Title	11,767	4.96	1	223,981
DC.Type	11,767	4.96	0	-
DC.Type.articleType	11,767	4.96	0	-
gs_meta_revision	11,767	4.96	0	-
citation_journal_title	11,767	4.96	0	-
citation_journal_abbrev	11,767	4.96	0	-
citation_issn	13,498	5.70	0	-
citation_author	11,767	4.97	0	-
citation_title	11,785	4.96	0	-
citation_language	11,767	4.96	0	-
citation_date	11,767	4.96	0	-
citation_volume	12,298	45.18	0	-
citation_issue	28,964	12.21	0	-
citation_firstpage	69,177	29.14	1	166,217
citation_lastpage	69,137	29.16	1	166,056
citation_abstract_html_url	11,767	4.96	0	-
citation_pdf_url	18,314	7.72	0	-
DC.Subject	114,973	48.46	1	121,399
citation_keywords	114,973	48.46	0	-

DC.Identifier.DOI	137,180	57.82	1	99,073
citation_doi	137,180	57.82	0	-
citation_author_institution	212,079	89.40	0	-
DC.Coverage	237,263	100	0	-
citation_reference	237,232	99.99	0	-
DC.Title.Alternative	237,263	100	0	-

2.2 Matching with OpenAlex

Articles were matched against the OpenAlex (Priem et al., 2022) data dump using journal names, DOIs, and other article metadata. The process was conducted in several steps, prioritizing accuracy at each stage. Rather than maximizing the number of matches, the approach focused on ensuring accuracy. After each step, checks were performed to remove any duplicate rows from the resulting table. Matched articles were removed from the initial AJOL table so that the remaining steps were applied only to non-matched articles. In cases of duplicate matches, duplicates were removed from the matched articles table and added back to the non-matched table for inclusion in subsequent steps.

- Exact match by DOI: A total of 80,667 matches were identified.
- Exact match by journal and title: 67,191 matches were found after excluding common titles (e.g., “introduction,” “review”) to avoid false positives.
- Exact match by journal and fuzzy title match: 7,265 matches were identified. To account for inconsistencies between databases, all titles were transformed to lowercase, and punctuation was removed. A Levenshtein distance threshold of less than 20 characters and a distance-to-title length proportion of less than 0.25 were applied to minimize errors. A sample of 100 matches was manually verified, and no errors were detected.
- Exact match by journal, year, issue, volume, and pages: 435 matches were identified in this step. Since the pages field can be inconsistent in both OpenAlex and AJOL, this step was performed last to reduce potential errors. All matches were manually checked, and 10 erroneous matches were removed.

In total, 155,558 articles were successfully matched out of 223,981 articles in AJOL. This aligns with recent studies on OpenAlex coverage. For example, Chavarro and Alperin (2024) reported that OpenAlex covers 70% of journals using the Open Journal System (OJS). Since AJOL does not record some metadata fields, matching AJOL with OpenAlex provides additional insights into the data, such as affiliation and institution analysis or collaboration patterns at different levels.

However, several important limitations related to the matching process must be acknowledged. The following three figures illustrate the percentage of articles indexed in OpenAlex based on the matching procedure described above, disaggregated by year, research field, and country. Figure 1 reveals that coverage rates for articles published before 1995 are significantly lower compared to those published thereafter. It is important to contextualize this finding by noting that the volume of publications in AJOL prior to 1995 is itself quite limited, typically ranging from 20 to 40 articles per year, with a few exceptions—for instance, AJOL recorded 83, 80, and 103 publications in 1987, 1988, and

1991, respectively. The number of indexed publications begins to increase in 1997 (198 publications), exceeds 1,000 in the year 2000, and consistently ranges between 10,000 and 15,000 annually from 2010 onward.

Figure 1. Percentage of publications not matched in OpenAlex by year

Figure 2 presents the proportion of non-matched publications by research area, bearing in mind that journals—and consequently their articles—can be assigned to up to three subject areas in AJOL. The figure indicates that certain fields, such as History and Communication and Library Science, exhibit relatively low coverage in OpenAlex, with over 50% of their publications not indexed. Most research areas, however, show coverage rates between 60% and 80%. Religion is the only field with a coverage rate exceeding 80%, with just 15% of its publications not included in OpenAlex.

Figure 2. Percentage of publications not matched in OpenAlex by research area (AJOL journal classification)

Regarding countries, Figure 3 shows that those with the highest number of journals indexed in AJOL—namely Nigeria and South Africa, with 78,918 and 60,091 publications respectively, compared to 21,904 from the next most productive country, Kenya—also exhibit the lowest levels of coverage in OpenAlex. In contrast, the percentage of unmatched publications for all other countries remains below 5%.

Figure 3. Percentage of publications not matched in OpenAlex by journal country

2.3 Data structure

The final database is divided in six tables, linking publications, journals, and related metadata. Figure 1 shows the database diagram- Table pub stores publication-level information, including DOIs, titles, and bibliographic data, and connects to supporting tables for abstracts, keywords, authors, and external identifiers (e.g., OpenAlex). The source table contains journal-level metadata, such as ISSNs, country, and quality classification (e.g., JPPS status), while the source_area table associates journals with research areas.

Figure 4. Database diagram

*pub_abstract table is hidden to avoid possible copyright issues.

3. Results

This section presents descriptive statistics of selected fields of the database.

3.1 Journals

Figure 2 shows the distribution of journals across African countries, with each country shaded based on the total number of journals it hosts. The color scale on the right indicates the number of journals per country, ranging from light green (low journal count) to dark green (high journal count).

The countries with the highest numbers of journals are Nigeria (298 journals) and South Africa (105 journals). Other countries with relatively high numbers of journals include Ethiopia (53 journals), Kenya (48 journals), and Ghana (38 journals), and Tanzania (36 journals). In contrast, many countries, especially in Central and Northern Africa, are home to only a few journals. For example, countries like Libya, Botswana, Namibia host only from 1 to 3 journals. Some countries show moderate levels of academic journals, with countries such as Algeria (19 journals), Zimbabwe (14 journals), and Cameroon and Uganda (13 journals) occupying the middle range. Countries such as Chad, Central African Republic, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mauritania, Mali, Namibia, Niger, Somalia, or Western Sahara do not appear in the map as they do not have any journals indexed in AJOL.

This map highlights significant disparities in the distribution of academic journals across Africa, with a concentration of journals in just a few countries. While countries like Nigeria and South Africa are major hubs for academic publishing, many other African nations have very limited journal output, or none at all, which reflects the disparities between countries even in a specialized source.

Figure 5. Number of journals by country

Figure 3 shows the distribution of journals across JPPS quality categories and type of access. The graph on the left highlights a concentration of journals in the 1 Star, 2 Stars, and No Stars categories. This suggests that while many journals meet basic standards, fewer journals reach the highest thresholds (3 Stars), and a significant portion of journals either fail to meet star rating criteria or are inactive.

The substantial number of Inactive Titles suggests that there are numerous journals that have ceased publishing but are still considered part of the AJOL, which highlights the role of the platform as an archive of African journals to improve its access and visibility regardless of them being active or not, differentiating it from traditional indexes, whose main objective is to index and rank active journals.

The graph on the right side of the Figure shows a higher number of diamond access journals than journals with other access types. This distribution is in line with AJOL policy of supporting open access and free-fee publication models.

Figure 6. Number of journals by JPPS category (left) and number of journals by access type (right)

3.2 Publications

Figure 4 presents the total number of publications by year (green bars) and the relative share of publications with Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) (orange line) over time. From the 1990s onwards, there is a significant increase in publications, reaching a peak between 2010 and 2020. The apparent decrease in 2024 is attributed to the data collection date – February 2024– meaning that publications released after this point were not yet included in the dataset.

The number of publications with DOIs follow a similar pattern to total publications, indicating the increasing adoption of DOIs as a standard identifier in scholarly publishing. The line remains aligned with the overall trend after 2000, suggesting that a significant proportion of publications since then have been assigned DOIs. However, despite the growth in publications continues until 2015, there is a slight decline in the number of DOIs. To better assess the causes of this decline, the metadata in AJOL was compared with the metadata available in OpenAlex, which revealed that the drop is a cause of changes in AJOL’s reporting practices rather than a decline in the adoption of DOIs.

Figure 7. Publications (bar plot) and publications with DOI (orange line) by publication year

Figure 5 presents the distribution of publications across different research areas, illustrating the total number of publications per area. In AJOL, research areas are assigned at the journal level, meaning that the research areas of the publications correspond to the fields of the journals. As the publications' areas depend on the journals' classification, they are both plot together for comparison. The x-axis lists the research areas, while the y-axis represents the number of journals (green bars) of publications (orange line).

Health dominates the distribution, with over 80,000 publications and 200 journals, making it by far the largest field in terms of output. Following Health, Biology and Life Sciences and Agriculture and Food Sciences also have significant publication numbers, though at considerably lower levels than health, each with between 30,000 to 40,000 publications. In the case of journals, Biology and Life Sciences and Humanities present the highest numbers after Health, followed by African Studies and Economics and Development. In both publications and journals, History, Philosophy, and Earth Sciences have the lowest representation, with fewer than 1,000 publications each.

The relationship between the number of journals and the number of publications is generally proportional, although fields like Agriculture & Food Science or Veterinary Science show higher publication output compared to their journal count. Other fields like Finance & Management show a lower publication output than the number of journals. Differences in the trends of journals and publications might be due to different publication patterns between journals. For instance, some journals in AJOL publish only one issue per year, while others publish one every few months. The number of papers per issue can also influence the relationship between the numbers of journals and papers.

Figure 8. Publications by research area (journal classification)

Figure 6 shows the number of publications in AJOL depending on the authors' country. For this visualization the matching between OpenAlex and AJOL was used and then merged with OpenAlex data dump. Author country data was found for 94,168 publications. No normalization was applied for articles with more than one author. The shading reflects the number of publications per country, with darker shades representing a higher number of publications and lighter shades indicating fewer publications. The scale, ranging from 250 to 1000 or more publications, is shown in the legend on the right. Few countries with a higher number of publications were skewing the scale, therefore the limits were adjusted to better represent the maximum number of countries. The number of publications of high-productive countries is reported below the graph.

The two most productive countries are Nigeria (25,450) and South Africa (24,213), followed by United States (5,354), China (3,863) and India (3,863). In Africa, other countries with high productivity are Ethiopia (3,132), Ghana (2,723), Kenya (2,461), Tanzania (1,970), Morocco (1,637), Egypt (1,479), Uganda (1,410), Cameroon (1,307), Benin (1,258), Ivory Coast (1,249), and Zimbabwe (1,225). The rest of the continent, particularly Central and Sahel regions show lighter shades, indicating lower publication outputs. Outside Africa, some countries in Europe and the Middle East show high publication outputs, while South America and the Southeast of Asia present lower values.

The color scale was adjusted to make differences between countries visible. However, there are some outliers whose number of publications exceeds the upper limit. These countries are: Nigeria – 25,450; South Africa – 24,213; United States – 5,354; China – 3,863; India – 3,362; Ethiopia – 3,041; Ghana – 2,628; Kenya – 2,359; Tanzania – 1,918; Turkey – 1,887; Iran – 1,683.

Figure 9. Number of publications by author country

The map highlights that African journals serve as international venues, attracting contributions from authors both within and outside the African continent. This global authorship pattern demonstrates the broad appeal and relevance of African-based journals in disseminating research across a variety of regions. Many authors from countries in the Global North, including the United States, the United Kingdom, and parts of Europe, contribute to African journals, suggesting that these journals are not only regionally focused but also engaged in the global exchange of knowledge.

4. Conclusions

This study highlights the potential of AJOL as a valuable bibliometric source for understanding African academic publishing. By systematically retrieving and structuring AJOL's data, this paper provides researchers with a more accessible and usable version of its metadata, filling a significant gap in bibliometric research focused on the African continent. It is worth mentioning that, while AJOL contains relevant information for identifying and providing insights about African publications and journals, its metadata is limited. This is however expected as AJOL is not an academic database but a journal repository designed to give visibility to African journals. Therefore, the article relies on web scraping techniques to retrieve available metadata and construct an accessible database.

The database introduced in this article contributes to the accessibility of African scholarly publications by providing structured, accessible metadata derived from AJOL. It facilitates bibliometric analyses that are more representative of African research activity. This contribution complements ongoing efforts to develop alternative data sources and

infrastructures that better reflect the diversity of global knowledge production, including those based on national repositories, regional indexes, and open metadata platforms. Moreover, by leveraging OpenAlex's additional metadata, this study demonstrates that metadata gaps can be partially addressed, enabling more detailed analyses of African research output. By doing so, it aims to contribute to the scientific decentralisation stated by Rodriguez-Medina (2014) and offers a new tool for bibliometric analysis that might help to mitigate coverage biases in bibliometric analysis on African scientific production.

The analysis of journals indexed in AJOL reveals significant disparities in their distribution across African countries. Nigeria and South Africa emerge as major hubs. This uneven distribution highlights the concentration of publishing resources in a few key countries, reflecting broader disparities in the African academic publishing landscape. It also shows that further efforts need to be made to expand the coverage of AJOL to the most underrepresented countries. Furthermore, the analysis of journals' quality categories using the JPPS framework shows that most journals fall into the 1 Star, 2 Stars, or No Stars categories, with relatively few reaching the highest (3 Stars) standards. The substantial number of Inactive Titles also underscores AJOL's role as an archival platform, distinguishing it from traditional indexing systems focused solely on active journals. The publication analysis demonstrates a steady growth in the number of publications over time. The analysis also highlights the increasing adoption of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), aligning with global trends in scholarly publishing. Biases towards Health sciences, Biology and Life Sciences are also observed in the analysis, while fields like Philosophy, History, and Earth Sciences remain underrepresented.

Finally, the inclusion of matched data with OpenAlex further enhances the utility of the database. The paper presents an example of the possibilities of integrating both sources using author country data from OpenAlex. The analysis of author contributions reveals that African journals serve as both regional and international venues. Further analysis might explore other areas like collaboration patterns, institutional affiliations, and citation networks, which cannot be addressed only with AJOL data. The ability to integrate AJOL with global databases demonstrates its capacity to contribute to a more inclusive and comprehensive representation of global science.

The findings confirm that African journals play a dual role in fostering both regional and global research engagement. As shown by the map of author contributions, African journals attract submissions from both African-based and international researchers. This underscores their importance as venues for disseminating locally relevant research while also participating in the global exchange of knowledge. However, the article also shows the important limitations of such data sources, both in terms of coverage and metadata, highlighting the importance of initiatives and efforts that address these issues, and help to provide a more comprehensive picture of African science. Finally, while this study reinforces AJOL's role in amplifying the visibility of African journals, it also raises broader questions about the role of such regional platforms in the global bibliometric ecosystem. Platforms like AJOL not only document African research but also serve as a counterbalance to the regional, linguistic, and disciplinary biases inherent in traditional data sources. However, their long-term impact will depend on continued investment in their development, stronger interoperability with global data infrastructures, and increased engagement from the scientific community to ensure their data is both comprehensive and widely used.

Conflict of interest

The author does not declare any conflict of interest.

Data availability

The database containing AJOL data is deposited in Zenodo: 10.5281/zenodo.15383374

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